

Additional information 1: NCBI Accession numbers of viruses used for primer design.

BMYV: X83110, NC_003491, KC121026, MW367423, DQ132996

BChV: MH271171, AF352024, AF352025, MW367424, NC_002766, MN734427

BYV: X73476, AF056575, MW274719, MT701720, MT815988, AF190581, NC_001598

BtMV: MT663309, MT815987, MT737808, DQ674264, KY012334, MT815986, DQ674263, AY206394, NC_005304, MW348911

TuYV: MT586571, MT586573, MT586576, MT586574, MT586575, MK616236, KR706247, MZ313372, MT955608, MT955609, OK030771, MN497803, OK030792, OK030798, MN497808, OK030791, OK030769, OK030785, OK030784, MN497810, MT955610, MT955611, OK030788, MT586582, MT586581, LC701523, MT586586, MT586585, MT586588, MT586587, LR584021, MT586577, MT586578, LR584019, MT586579, LR584020, MT586580, MT586589, MT586590, LR584026, LR584027, LR584025, MT586584, MT586583, OK030793, X13063, NC_003743, MT586597, MT586598, OK030772, OK030770, MN497809, MN497800, OK030789, OK030794, OK030773, OK030774, OK030780, MN497806, MN497807, MN497805, MN497802, OK030750, OK030782, OK030767, OK030783, OK030778, MN497811, MK450519, MW854285, KU198395, MT586591, MT586594, MT586593, MT586592, OK030781, MZ442681, MZ442680, MZ442679, MN497804, OK030790, MN497801, MK450520, MT955607, MT586595, LR584024, JQ862472, MT586596, KU726091, KU726090

Additional information 2: Sequences of virus amplicons generated in the one-step multiplex RT-PCR (mRT-PCR)

BMYV 1 (594 bp)

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AGCAGCTCGACCCTGGGAGCCTCGTTTACTCTCCCGGAAACGCCAGTCTTTACGACTGG
CCCGGTTCTACAATTACTGCGGAACCGCTTTGCCAGCACTCGCAACGTTGACTTACGAGT
GCCCCCAGAAAAGACGTTAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCGAAATTCAGGCAGAAATCTGGG
GGAGAGGCTACAACGCCGTGGAGAAATTTCTTTACGGTGAAGCAGAGTTTAAAAGTT
CCTTTCAGTATGGTGTGCTGAAAGCGAAAGAAAATTACGGGAGAGCCCTAAGATCAACATT
AAAATGGATCGTATTATTATGGTCTTACGTGATATGGGCACTCTCTTGCACCGCCTGGTATTT
GTTGAAGAACTATAACCATAGAAATACTTATGCTGAGCTCGCTTTTTGCGTTCACCACCTTTT
TGGTGAAGCTCGCGGTATGGATTTTTGGCGGTTGGCTAACTCCCTGGTAAATGGTTTATTT
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GCTCTCACGAAACGTATCTTGAAAACCTTTTCATCCAGAAAGAGCTACGTTTGTGAGCGGT
CTGTGAAAGGTTTTCTCACCTTTACCATCAAACAAAAGCCCGAA

BMV 2(538 bp)

CGCCAGTCTCTACGACTGGCCCGGTTCTACAATTACTGCGGAACCGCGTTACCCAGCACTC
GCAACATTGACTTACGAGTGCCCCCAGAAAAGACGTTAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCGAA
ATTCAGGCAGAAATCTGGGGGAGAGGCTACAACGCCGTAGAGAGATTTTCTCTCACGGTG
AAGCAGAGTTTAAAAGTTCCCTTTCAGTATGGTGTGCTGAAAGCGAAAAGAAAATTACGGG
AGAGCCCTAAGATCAACATTAATAATGGAGCATATTATTATGGTCTTACGTGATATGGGCACT
CTCTTGCACCGTCTGGTATTTGTTGAAGAACTATAACCATAGAAATACTTATGCTGAGCTCGC
TTTTTGCCTCACCACCTTTTTTGGTGAAGCTCGCGGTATGGATTTTTGGCGGTTGGCTAACT
TCCCTGGTAAATGGTTTATTTGCTCTCACGAAACGTATCTTGAAAACCTTTTCATCCAGAAA
GAGCTACGTTTGTGAGCGATCTGTAAAAGGTTTTCTCACCTTTACCATC

BMV 3 (585 bp)

GCTCACCTGGGAGCCTCATTACACTCCCGGGAAACGCCAGTCTCTACGACTGGCCCGGT
TCTACAATTACTGCGGAACCGCGTTGCCCAGCACTCGCAGCATTGACTTACGAGTGTCCCC
CAGAAAAGACGTTAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCGAAATTCAGGCAGAAATCTGGGGGAGAG
GCTACAACGCCGTAGAGAGATTTTCTTTCACGGTGAAGCAGAGTTTAAAAGTTCCCTTTCA
GTGTGGTGTGCTGAAAGCGAAAAGAAAATTACGGGAGAGCCCTAAGATCAACATTAATAATG
GAGCATACTATTATGGTCTTACGTGATATGGGCACTCTCTTGCACCGTCTGGTATTTGTTGAA
GAACTATAACCATAGAAATACTTATGCTGAGCTCGCTTTTTTGCCTCACCACCTTTTTGGTGA
AGCTCGCGGTATGGATTTTTTGGCGGTTGGCTAACTTCCCTGGTAAATGGTTTATTTGCTCTC
ACGAAACGTATCTTGAAAACCTTTTCATCCAGAAAGAGCTACGTTTGTGAGCGATCTGTGA
AAGGTTTTCTCACCTTTACCATCAAACAAAAGCCC

BMV 4 (590 bp)

TCATTACACTCCCGGGAAACGCCAGTCTCTACGACTGGCCCGGTTCTACAATTACTGCGG
AACCGCGTTGCCCAGCACTCGCAGCATTGACTTACGAGTGTCCCCCAGAAAAGACGTTAA
AAGATTTTACCTTGCCCGAAATTCAGGCAGAAATCTGGGGGAGAGGCTACAACGCCGTAG
AGAGATTTTCTTTCACGGTGAAGCAGAGTTTAAAAGTTCCCTTTCAGTGTGGTGTGCTGAA
AGCGAAAAGAAAATTACGGGAGAGCCCTAAGATCAACATTAATAATGGAGCATACTATTATGG
TCTTACGTGATATGGGCACTCTCTTGCACCGTCTGGTATTTGTTGAAGAACTATAACCATAGA
AACTTATGCTGAGCTCGCTTTTTTGCCTCACCACCTTTTTTGGTGAAGCTCGCGGTATGGA
TTTTTGGCGGTTGGCTAACTTCCCTGGTAAATGGTTTATTTGCTCTCACGAAACGTATCTTG
AAAACCTTTTCATCCAGAAAGAGCTACGTTTGTGAGCGATCTGTGAAAGGTTTTCTCACCT
TTACCATCAAACAAAAGCCC

BMV 5 (214 bp)

GCCTCGTTTACACTCCCAGGAAACGCCAGTCTTTACGACTGGCCAGGTTCTACAATTACTG
CGGAACCGCCCTGCCAGCACTCGCAACGTTGACTTACGAGTGCCCCCACAAAAGACGT
TAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCGAAATTCAGGCAGAGTTCTGGGGGAGAGGCTACAACGCCG
CAGAGAAATTTCTCTCGCGGTGAAGCAGAGTT

BChV 1 (180 bp)

TCCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCTACTAACACAGGACTCCGTGTG
GGACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGATTACAGCTACAAAGAACTTGTAATACACGTC
TTGCAAAGAGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAACCTAGGCCATCAATGG

BChV 2 (241 bp)

GAGCTCTTGGGACCATGGCACCATCTTATATGGTGACAGGCCCTTTACACGCGCCGAAGAT
CTCCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCTACTAACACAGGACTCCGTGT
GGACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGACTACAGCTACAAAGAACTTGTAATACACGTC
CTTGCAAAGAGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAACCTAGGCCATCAATGA

BChV 3 (257 bp)

AGCTCTTGGGACCATGGCACCATCTTATATGGTGACAGGCCCTTTACACGCGCCGAAGATC
TCCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCTACTAACACAGGACTCCGTGTG
GGACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGATTACAGCTACAAAGAACTTGTAATACACGTC
TTGCAAAGAGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAACCTAGCATCAATGAGTCAC
TGCATGCAGAGAC

BChV 4 (241 bp)

GGAGCTCTTGGGACCATGGCACCATCTTATATGGTGACAGGCCCTTTACACGCGCCGAAGA
TCTCCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCTACTAACACAGGACTCCGTG
TGGGACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGATTACAGCTACAAAGAACTTGTAATACACG
TCTTGCAAAGAGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAACCTAGCATCAATGA

BYV 1 (450 bp)

CTTACTGCGTAGTCACTGCGGCCACGCCGAGTACCACGCTGCTTTAACTATTGCGCGTGG
CGATCGCCCTCGCATTGGTGAACCTTTGCAGTACCGACCCGGCGAAGGGTTATGTTACCTC
GCCACGCCGCTCTTTGTTGCGCTCTTCAGAAGCGCACCTTTCGCGAAGAAGACTTCTTCG
TTGGTTTGTACCCGACGAAGTTTGTCTTCGCTAAACGACTCACTGAAAAGTTGGGTCCTAG
TGTTCTCAAACATCCTGTGCGCGGAAGACAAGTCTCTCGTTCACTCTTCCACTGTGATGTG
GCCTCTGCTTTTTTCGAGCCCCTTCTACAGTTTGCCGCGTTTCATCGGCGGCGTGGAAGAAG

AAGCTCCTGAGATCACGTCGTCTCTTAAGCACAAGGCGATCGAATCAGTCTACGAACGTGT
CAGCATTACAAAAAGACAACAA

BYV 2 (445 bp)

CTTACTGCGTAGTCACTGCGGCCACGCCGAGTACCACGCTGCTTTAACTATTGCGCGTGG
CGATCGCCCTCGCGTCGGTGAACTTTTGCAGTACCGACCCGGCGAAGGGTTATGTTACCTC
GCCACGCCGCTCTTTGTTGCGCTCTTCAGAAGCGCACCTTTCGCGAAGAAGACTTCTTCG
TTGGTTTGTACCCGACGAAGTTTATCTTCGCTAAACGACTCACTGAAAAGTTGGGTCTAG
TGTTCTCAAACATCCTGTGCGCGGAAGACAAGTCTCTCGTTCCTTCCACTGTGATGTG
GCCTCTGCTTTTTTCGAGCCCCTTCTACAGTTTGCCGCGTTTCGTCGGCGGCGTGGAAGAAG
ATGCTCCTGAGATCACGTCGTCTCTTAAGCACAAGGCGATCGAGTCAGTCTACGAACGTGT
CAGCATTACAAAGACAACAA

BYV 3 (442 bp)

ACTGCGTGGTCACCGCGGCTATGCCGCGGTATCACGCCGCTTAACTATAGCGCGTGGTGA
ACGTCCTCGCGTTGGTGAACATAATGCAGTACAGCCCTGGTGAGGGTTTGTGTTACCTCGCC
CACGCCGCCCTTTGCTGCGCTCTTCAGAAGCGCACCTTTCGTGAAGAGGATTTCTTCGTCCG
GTTTGTACCCGACGAAGTTCGTCTTCGCTAGACGACTCACTGAAAAGTTGGGTCTATTGC
CCTCAAGCATCCCCGCGCGGCAGACAAGTCTCTCGCTCACTCTTCCATTGTGACGTAGCT
TCCACATTCTCGAGCCCCTTCTATAGTTTGCCGCGTTACCTCGGCGGCACGGAAGAAGAAG
CTCCTGAGATCACGTCGTCTCGTAAGCACAAGGCCATCGAATCAGTCTACGAACGCGTCAG
CATTACAAAGACAACAA

BYV 4 (433 bp)

CTGCGTAGTCACTGCGGCCACGCCGAGTACCACGCTGCTTTAACTATTGCGCGTGGCGAT
CGCCCTCGCGTTGGTGAACTTTTGCAGTACCGACCCGGCGAAGGGTTATGTTACCTCGCCC
ACGCCGCTCTTTGTTGCGCTCTTCAGAAGCGCACCTTTCGCGAAGAAGACTTCTTCGTTGG
TTTGTACCCGACGAAGTTTGTCTTCGCTAAACGACTCACTGAAAAGTTGGGTCTAGTGT
CTCAAACATCCTGTGCGCGGAAGACAAGTCTCTCGTTCCTTCCACTGTGATGTGGCCT
CTGCTTTTTTCGAGCCCCTTCTACAGTTTGCCGCGTTTCATCGGCGGCGTGGAAGAAGAAGC
TCCTGAGATCACGTCGTCTCTTAAGCACAAGGCGATCGAATCAGTCTACGAACGTGTCAGC
ATTCAC

TuYV (131 bp)

TTCTTCGCTCTCTGCTCTATCAGCTTCCTCTCCACCTCGGAGACCACGTCCACGATGACGTT
AGGAAGTCCTTACTTGTCCCCGAACCAGAGCTTTGCGCCTGGTTCTCTTTACAAACGGGAT
ATGCTCAA

Additional information 3: A comparison between the two-step PCR protocol and the one-step mRT-PCR protocol for the detection of yellowing viruses in sugar beet.

RNA code IRS	Two-step RT-PCR results			One-step mRT-PCR results		
	BYV	BChV	BMVYV	BYV	BChV	BMVYV
4095	-	+	+	-	+	+
4103	-	+	+	-	+	+
4137	-	+	+	-	+	+
4217	+	-	+	+	+/-	+
4384	+	+	-	+	+	-
5093	+	+	-	+	+	-
5110	+	+	-	+	+	-
5140	+	-	-	+	+	+/-
5143	+	-	-	+	+/-	+/-
5147	+/-	-	+	-	-	+
5180	+	-	+	+	-	+
5182	+	+	-	+	+	+
5230	-	+	-	-	+	-
5426	-	-	+	-	-	+
5428	-	-	+	-	-	+
5430	-	+	-	-	+	-
5432	-	+	+	+/-	+	+
6220	-	-	+	-	-	+
6221	-	+	-	-	+	-
6223	-	-	+	-	-	+

Samples send for sequencing:

RNA code	Product size:	Primers	Primer direction	Macrogen
4217	491	BYV_Fw_TSPE_1473	forward	1FBAZAC054
4217	296	BChV_Fw_166	forward	1FBAZAC053
5140	491	BYV_Fw_TSPE_1473	forward	1FBAZAC052
5140	296	BChV_Fw_166	forward	1FBAZAC051
5140	632	BMVYV_Fw_165	forward	1FBAZAC050
5143	296	BChV_Fw_166	forward	1FBAZAC049
5143	632	BMVYV_Fw_165	forward	1FBAZAC048
5182	632	BMVYV_Fw_165	forward	1FBAZAC047
5432	491	BYV_Fw_TSPE_1473	forward	1FBAZAC046
5432	296	BChV_Fw_166	forward	1FBAZAC045
5432	632	BMVYV_Fw_165	forward	1FBAZAC044
5147		IRS_Fw	forward	1FBAZAC058

BMVY (1FBAZAC044)

CCTGGGACCTCATTACACTCCCAGGAAACGCCAGTCTCTACGACTGGCCCCGGTTCTACAA
TTACTGCGGAACCGCGTTACCCAGCACTCGCAACATTGACTTACGAGTGCCCCCAGAAA
AGACGTTAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCCGAAATTCAGGCAGAAATCTGGGGGAGAGGCTACA
ACGCCGTAGAGAGATTTTCTCTCACGGTGAAGCAGAGTTTAAAAAGTTCCTTTCAGTATGG
TGTGCTGAAAGCGAAAGAAAATTACGGGAGAGCCCTAAGATCAACATTAATAATGGAGCAT
ATTATTATGGTCTTACGTGATATGGGCACTCTCTTGACCGTCTGGTATTTGTTGAAGAACTA
TACCATAGAAATACTTATGCTGAGCTCGCTTTTTGCGTTCACCACCTTTTTGGTGAAGCTCG
CGGTATGGATTTTTGGCGGTTGGCTAACTTCCCTGGTAAATGGTTTATTTGCTCTCACGAAA
CGTATCTTGAAAACCTTTTCATCCAGAAAGAGCTACGTTTGTGAGCGATCTGTAAAAGGTT
TTCTCACCTTTACC

1FBAZAC045 (BChV)

GCTCTTGGGACCATGGCACCATCTTATATGGTGACAGGCCCTTACACGCGCCGAAGATCT
CCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCCTACTAACACAGGACTCCGTGTGG
GACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGACTACAGCTACAAAGAACTTGTAAATACACGTCT
TGCAAAGAGGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAACCTAGGCATCAATGAG

1FBAZAC046 (BYV)

TACTGCGTAGTCACTGCGGCCACGCCGACGTACCACGCTGCTTTAACTATTGCGCGTGGCG
ATCGCCCTCGCGTCGGTGAACCTTTTGCAGTACCGACCCGGCGAAGGGTTATGTTACCTCGC
CCACGCCGCTCTTTGTTGCGCTCTTCAGAAGCGCACCTTTCGCGAAGAAGACTTCTTCGTT
GGTTTGTACCCGACGAAGTTTATCTTCGCTAAACGACTCACTGAAAAGTTGGGTCTTAGTG
TTCTCAAACATCCTGTGCGCGGAAGACAAGTCTCTCGTTCCTTCCACTGTGATGTGGC
CTCTGCTTTTTCGAGCCCCTTCTACAGTTTGCCGCGTTTCGTTCGGCGGCGTGGAAGAAGAT
GCTCCTGAGATCACGTCGTCTTAAAGCACAAGGCGATCGAGTCAGTCTACGAACGTGTCA
GCATTCACAAAGACAAC

1FBAZAC047 (BMVY)

AGCTCACCTGGGAGCCTCATTACACTCCCAGGAAACGCCAGTCTCTACGACTGGCCCG
GTTCTACAATTACTGCGGAACCGCGTTGCCAGCACTCGCAGCATTGACTTACGAGTGTCC
CCCAGAAAAGACGTTAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCCGAAATTCAGGCAGAAATCTGGGGGAG
AGGCTACAACGCCGTAGAGAGATTTTCTTTCACGGTGAAGCAGAGTTTAAAAAGTTCCTTT
CAGTGTGGTGTGCTGAAAGCGAAAGAAAATTACGGGAGAGCCCTAAGATCAACATTAATA

TGGAGCATACTATTATGGTCTTACGTGATATGGGCACTCTCTTGCACCGTCTGGTATTTGTTG
AAGAACTATAACCATAGAAATACTTATGCTGAGCTCGCTTTTTGCGTTCACCACCTTTTTGGT
GAAGCTCGCGGTATGGATTTTTGGCGGTTGGCTAACTTCCTGGTAAATGGTTTATTTGCTC
TCACGAAACGTATCTTGAAAACCTTTTCATCCAGAAAGAGCTACGTTTGTGAGCGATCTGT
GAAAGGTTTTCTCACCTTTACCATCAAACAAAGCCCG

1FBAZAC048 (BMYV (Bad quality Sanger results))

TTTACGACTGGCCAGGTTCTACAATTACTGCGGAACCGCCCTGCCAGCACTCGCAACGTT
GACTTACGAGTGCCCCCACAAAAGACGTTAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCGAAATTCAGGCA
GAGTTCTGGGGGAGAGGCTACAACGCCGAGAGAAATTTCTCTCGCGGTGAAGCAGAGT
TTAAAAGTTCCTTTCAGTATGGTGTGCTGAAAGCGAAAGAAAGCTACGGGAGAGCCCTA
AAATTGATATTAGAAGGGACCGGATGATTATGGTCCTACCTGCTATGGGCCCTCTCTTGCC
CGTCTGGTAGTTGTTGAACAACCTATCCCAGAGATATACTTATGCTGAGCTCGGTTTTTGC
TCACCATCTTTTTGGTGAACCTCCCGG

1FBAZAC049 (BChV)

GGAGCTCTTGGGACCATGGCACCATCTTATATGGTGACAGGCCCTTTACACGCGCCGAAGA
TCTCCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCCTACTAACACAGGACTCCGTG
TGGGACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGATTACAGCTACAAAGAAGTTGTAATACAG
TCTTGCAAAGAGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAACCTAGCATCAATGAGTC
ACTGCATGCAGAGACCATCTTGTTGCTCGTCCTTGCGATCATC

1FBAZAC050 (BMYV)

ACCTGGGAGCCTCATTTACACTCCCGGGAAACGCCAGTCTCTACGACTGGCCCGGTTCTAC
AATTACTGCGGAACCGCGTTGCCAGCACTCGCAGCATTGACTTACGAGTGTCCCCCAGAA
AAGACGTTAAAAGATTTTACCTTGCCCGAAATTCAGGCAGAAATCTGGGGGAGAGGCTAC
AACGCCGTAGAGAGATTTTCTTTACGGTGAAGCAGAGTTTAAAAGTTCCTTTCAGTGTG
GTGTGCTGAAAGCGAAAGAAAATTACGGGAGAGCCCTAAGATCAACATTAATGAGCA
TACTATTATGGTCTTACGTGATATGGGCACTCTCTTGCACCGTCTGGTATTTGTTGAAGAACT
ATACCATAGAAATACTTATGCTGAGCTCGCTTTTTGCGTTCACCACCTTTTTGGTGAAGCTC
GCGGTATGGATTTTTGGCGGTTGGCTAACTTCCTGGTAAATGGTTTATTTGCTCTCACGAA
ACGTATCTTGAAAACCTTTTCATCCAGAAAGAGCTACGTTTGTGAGCGATCTGTGAAAGGT
TTTTCTCACCTTTACCATCAAACAAAGCCCG

1FBAZAC051 (BChV)

GCTCCTAATCTTATTTGGAGCTCTTGGGACCATGGCACCATCTTATATGGTGACAGGCCCTT
TACACGCGCCGAAGATCTCCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCCTACTA

ACACAGGACTCCGTGTGGGACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGATTACAGCTACAAA
GAACTTGTAATACACGTCTTGCAAAGAGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAA
CTAGCATCAATGA

1FBAZAC052 (BYV)

GCTTACTGCGTGGTCACCGCGGCTATGCCGCGGTATCACGCCGCCTTAACTATAGCGCGTG
GTGAACGTCTCGCGTTGGTGAACATAATGCAGTACAGCCCTGGTGAGGGTTTGTGTTACCT
CGCCCACGCCGCCCTTTGCTGCGCTCTTCAGAAGCGCACCTTTCGTGAAGAGGATTTCTTC
GTCGGTTTGTACCCGACGAAGTTCGTCTTCGCTAGACGACTCACTGAAAAGTTGGGTCCTA
TTGCCCTCAAGCATCCCCCGCGCGGCAGACAAGTCTCTCGCTCACTCTTCCATTGTGACGT
AGCTTCCACATTCTCGAGCCCCTTCTATAGTTTGGCGCGTTACCTCGGCGGCACGGAAGAA
GAAGCTCCTGAGATCACGTCTCGTAAGCACAAGGCCATCGAATCAGTCTACGAACGC
GTCAGCATTACAAAGACAACA

1FBAZAC053 (BChV)

AGCTCCTATCTTATTTGGAGCTCTTGGGACCATGGCACCATCTTATATGGTGACAGGCCCTT
TACACGCGCCGAAGATCTCCTCAGATTTTCCCTTACCACCGGATATTACCCAACCTCCTACTA
ACACAGGACTCCGTGTGGGACTGCCCTCTTCAGAAAAAGCTATCAGATTACAGCTACAAA
GAACTTGTAATACACGTCTTGCAAAGAGGCTACAACGACACCCAGAAATACTTGCCACAA
CTAGCATCAATGA

1FBAZAC054 (BYV)

CTGCGTAGTCACTGCGGCCACGCCGAGTACCACGCTGCTTTAACTATTGCGCGTGGCGAT
CGCCCTCGCGTTGGTGAACTTTTGCAGTACCGACCCGGCGAAGGGTTATGTTACCTCGCCC
ACGCCGCTCTTTGTTGCGCTCTTCAGAAGCGCACCTTTCGCGAAGAAGACTTCTTCGTTGG
TTTGTACCCGACGAAGTTTGTCTTCGCTAAACGACTCACTGAAAAGTTGGGTCCTAGTGTT
CTCAAACATCCTGTGCGCGGAAGACAAGTCTCTCGTTCCTTCCACTGTGATGTGGCCT
CTGCTTTTTTCGAGCCCCTTCTACAGTTTGGCGCGTTTCATCGGCGGCGTGGAAGAAGAAGC
TCCTGAGATCACGTCTCTTAAGCACAAGGCGATCGAATCAGTCTACGAACGTGTCAGC
ATTCACAAAAGACAACAAA

1FBAZAC058 (BYV IRS primers)

TGATTTTCTTTAGTGTATCGTACTTGAGTTCTGACATGGGATCAGCCGAACCTATAAGTGCA
ATCGCGACTTTTGAACCGTGAGTCTCGCAGACCAAACGTGTTTGCACGGTGAAGACTGC
GACAACTACGGAAGAATTTTGAAGAGTGTGTTGAAATTGAAAGGGGTCCGGAAGACAA
ACTCGGTCTCGCGTTAGGACTTTGTTTGTATTCTGTGCGACGATAGGTACTTCTAATAAAG
TTAGTGTCCAACCGACGTCTACTTTCATCAAAGCTTCGTTTCGGTGGTGGGAAGGAATTGTT

CCTCACTCACGGTGAAGTCTTTTCTGGACTCTCAGAACTTTTGGAAAGGAAAGCC
TAACAAGTTGCGTTGTTTCTGCCGCACTTTTCAGAAGGACTACATATCCTTCGCGAAGGAA
TACCGAGGAAGACTGCCTCCGATTGCTAGAGCCAACCGTCACGGTCTACCTGCTGAAGATC
ACTACTTAGCTGCTGATTTTCATATCGACATCAACAGAAGTTACTGACCTACAACAAGGTCGT
CTGCTGTTGGCGCGCGAAAACGCCACTCACACAGAGTTCTCGTCTGAATCACCAGTAACT
AGTTTGAAACAGCTGGGTCTGTTCTAGCCACCGGAAGATGATTGGCTCTGTGCGAAGTAG
CTCAGACGAGACCCTTTTTTAGAGTATTACTGTTAAAGGGTTTCGTTTATTATATTGTTGCAA
TCGAAACAGAAGAAGAACCATCTGAAGCTGAAGTTCCCTTTGGTATTACCTCCAAAAAAA
AAAACTAACTACAACACAAAAAACAACCAAAAACCCAGGCGCTCTCCCCAAC
CCCCCCCCCTCCACCCCCTTTTTTTAAAAAAAATTTTTTTTCATCCAATCCCTTATCCCC
TTTTTAATTATCTTCTTATCTTTTTTTTACACTATAAAAATTA AAAACTCAACATAATTATCT
TTATTTCTTAATTTTTTCCTTATAAATCATTCTTTTTTTTCTTTTTCCCTTACACCCATTTTAT
ATTTTCATATCACAAATAATATCATTTACAAAATGCTAATCATTATCTAATTTATTTACAATT
AACTATCTCCTAAACTATTTTTTTATAATAATAATCCATTCTCTCTACATTTTTTTTTTTATTT
AAATACATATTCACCCTATCAATTATAATTTCTTTCCTATTTAATTTATATAATTTTTTCCCTC
ATTATTATTATTTTTTTTTCCCTCCTTGAATTTAATTGCTCAACCTATATAATTATCTATATTTTT
TACCTACCTACGCATAACTGCTTATTTGATATTTTAGGATTTTTCTTGAGGTTTGATGTATACA
ATATTATGTT

Additional information 4: Results of the gel electrophoreses of outer primer amplifcons for the Target-Specific Primer Extension-Luminex assay tested on single virus-infected plant material.

	RNA code (IRS)	Viral RNA
1	5229	BMYV
2	5194	BMYV
3	5026	BMYV
4	7306	BMYV
5	8020	BMYV
6	PC	BMYV
7	NC	
9	4221	BYV
10	5294	BYV
11	5513	BYV
12	7999	BYV
13	8047	BYV
14	PC	BYV
15	NC	

	RNA code (IRS)	Viral RNA
17	5190	BChV
18	5430	BChV
19	7144	BChV
20	7164	BChV
21	7602	BChV
22	PC	BChV
23	PC	BChV
24	NC	
25	5201	BtMV
26	6223	BtMV
27	PC	BtMV
28	NC	
30	NC	
31	PC	TuYV

Results of outer primer amplifications of the field samples infected with single viruses. Amplicons were subsequently used for xTAG Array Technology. Samples were infected with beet yellows virus (BYV), beet mild yellowing virus

(BMV), beet chlorosis virus (BChV), beet mosaic virus (BtMV) and turnip yellows virus (TuYV). In the negative controls (NC) water instead of RNA was added.

Additional information 5: Results of the outer primer amplifications in the TSPE-Luminex assay gel electrophoreses.

	RNA code (IRS)	Target
1	5229 + 4221 + 5190	BMV + BYV + BChV
2	5194 + 5294 + 5430	BMV + BYV + BChV
3	5026 + 5513 + 7144	BMV + BYV + BChV
4	5229 + 4221	BMV + BChV
5	5194 + 5294	BMV + BYV
6	5026 + 5513	BMV + BYV
7	5229 + 5190	BMV + BChV
8	5164 + 5430	BMV + BChV
9	5026 + 7144	BMV + BChV
10	4221 + 5190	BYV + BChV
11	5294 + 5430	BYV + BChV
12	5513 + 7144	BYV + BChV
13	5229 + 4221 + 5190 + 5201	BMV + BYV + BChV + BtMV

	RNA code (IRS)	Target
16	5194 + 5294 + 5430 + 6223 + TuYV (PC)	BMV + BYV + BChV + BtMV + TuYV
17	X	Water
18	BChV (PC)	BChV
19	7980	BChV
20	7980	NAD5
21	5229	Generic poleroproprimer
22	5190	Generic poleroproprimer
23	TuYV (PC)	Generic poleroproprimer
24	X	Water
25	5229	Generic poleroproprimers 2
26	5190	Generic poleroproprimers 2
27	TuYV (PC)	Generic poleroproprimers 2
28	X	Water

14	5194 + 5294 + 5430 + 6223	BMVYV + BYV + BChV + BtMV	29	5194 + 5294 + 5430 + 6223 + TuYV (PC)	BMVYV + BYV + BChV + BtMV + TuYV + generic poloroprimer
15	5229 + 4221 + 5190 + 5201 + TuYV (PC)	BMVYV + BYV + BChV + BtMV + TuYV	30	5194 + 5294 + 5430 + 6223 + TuYV (PC)	5194 + 5294 + 5430 + 6223 + TuYV PC + generic poloroprimer 2

Results of multiplex Target specific primer extension-Luminex assays with all five outer primer pairs combined on different mixes of RNA isolated from virus infected field samples. Samples were infected with beet yellows virus (BYV; 491bp), beet mild yellowing virus (BMVYV; 632bp), beet chlorosis virus (BChV; 297bp), beet mosaic virus (BtMV; 834bp) and turnip yellows virus (TuYV); 142bp.